

Adaptive QoE optimization in non-stationary networks: Integrating PPO and digital twins for video streaming[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Video streaming has emerged as a dominant mode of entertainment and information dissemination. However, traditional approaches to video bitrate adaptation often fall short in non-stationary network environments, leading to suboptimal user experiences. To address these challenges, this work presents an innovative method leveraging Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm, to optimize the Quality of Experience (QoE) in video streaming scenarios. A Network Digital Twin (NDT) environment, which allows to emulate production environments, and the end, facilitate high-fidelity training and evaluation while completely isolating live network operations from experimental risks. The PPO algorithm learns to make bitrate decisions based on a reward function that incorporates key QoE metrics, including blockiness and block loss, achieving an impressive 73.02% enhancement in overall performance. Experimental results demonstrate a significant reduction in block loss (66.87%) and an improvement in blockiness (6.40%), while also increasing the streaming bitrate (17.18%) from training to production deployment.

1. Introduction

In the modern era of digital content consumption, video streaming has emerged as a dominant mode of entertainment and information dissemination. The rapid growth in demand for high-quality video content requires robust solutions to optimize the Quality of Experience (QoE) for end-users [1,2]. Conventional methods for adjusting video bitrate frequently underperform in fluctuating network conditions, resulting in poor user experiences with issues such as buffering, reduced resolution, and other visual distortions.

The shift towards ultra-dense 5G/6G access, heterogeneous end-devices, and immersive applications such as cloud gaming, VR/AR and multi-angle 360 degrees live events now imposes latency, reliability, and fairness requirements that far exceed those contemplated by classical Adaptive Bit-Rate (ABR) logic [3,4]. This upcoming and transformative scenario brings new requirements that cannot be easily managed by traditional solutions. Beyond 5G networks require a broader scope

of quality of service, introducing new scenarios where the desired behavior can vary. Novel use cases as the AR/VR might require ultra-low latency, massive streaming events will require minimum jitter and smart industry will need massive machine-type communications. Wireless cells and edge links can swing from tens of Mbps to sub-Mbps in a single RTT [5], while video clients differ drastically in display resolution and buffer size [6]. Meanwhile, the services are not the only ones to change, the number and characteristics of connected devices also increases, bringing a heterogeneous scenario that brings one more level of complexity to the equation. Such volatility magnifies the cost of every sub-optimal bitrate decision: a single stall or rebuffering event can halve session-level engagement and, in subscription contexts, directly erode revenue [7–9]. Consequently, there is a growing need for learning-based controllers that (i) react within milliseconds, (ii) anticipate longer-horizon congestion patterns, and (iii) remain robust when traffic mixes, mobility patterns, or codec generations change [10].

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Reinforcement Learning (RL) agents promise exactly that adaptability, yet training them safely is notoriously difficult. Live experimentation exposes paying users to the agent's inevitable early-stage trial and error, causing controversy in network SLAs [11,12]. A further obstacle is cold-start: when a freshly deployed model sees an unfamiliar network it must explore aggressively before converging [13]. Recent work therefore advocates off-policy pre-training in a Network Digital Twin (NDT), a high-fidelity software clone that mirrors topology and traffic in almost real time [14]. This concept has been previously explored in recent literature, both in researching articles [15,16] and in standardization bodies [17,18]. The NDT will bring to this work the advantage of being non-intrusive, allowing to make decisions over a realistic scenario without interfering with the real network nor the physical infrastructure. Also, the use of accurate real network data for ML training enhancing the goals of using these technologies and reducing the assumptions is translated into more precised results [19]. By rehearsing thousands of hours of synthetic congestion patterns inside the twin, the agent can learn a reward surface that balances the QoE without ever impacting production users [20]. More importantly, the twin enables rapid reaction and continual fine-tuning, shrinking the sim-to-real gap and eliminating the cold-start window once the policy is promoted to the physical network [21,22].

To confront these challenges, we propose a state of the art RL bitrate controller built on Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO). The agent is trained exclusively inside a NDT that emulates the production topology, traffic bursts, and the bandwidth footprints of co-located services, letting it explore multiple scenarios without disturbing live viewers. Policy's actions are executed directly on the operational streaming stack, where decisions are issued to track actual link conditions using the components deployed on the environment. This sim-to-real workflow eliminates cold-start fragility and delivers a controller that arrives in production pre-adapted to the disturbances it will face, consistently elevating end-user QoE under highly volatile networks.

Existing literature often struggles with the reality. The performance drop observed when transitioning RL models from simplified simulations to complex, physical network infrastructures. Traditional heuristic-based and off-policy RL controllers frequently fail to account for the non-linear relationship between network congestion and perceptual video artifacts like blockiness or frame freezing. The novelty of this work lies in the architectural synchronization between the NDT and the physical environment via a dedicated NDT Manager, which enables the PPO agent to internalize real-time telemetry from a high-fidelity emulation.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 surveys the state of the art in ABR streaming, specifically for RL agents; and emerging NDT frameworks, highlighting open gaps that motivate our approach. Section 3 formalizes the problem by describing the real-world streaming pipeline, the QoE driven reward model, and the real-time telemetry exposed by the NDT. Section 4 reports and analyzes the results. Section 5 compares with existing state of the art implementations. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines avenues for future work, including continual fine-tuning and multi-objective extensions.

2. Related works

This section reviews the evolution of adaptive bitrate strategies, moving from traditional heuristic methods to modern Reinforcement Learning approaches. We examine the role of NDTs, and the collaboration with RL to close the simulation to reality gap, motivating our research framework.

In recent years, the focus on enhancing the QoE in video streaming [23–25] has led to significant advancements in ABR streaming algorithms [26–28]. Traditional approaches such as DASH [29–32] and HLS [33,34] have employed heuristic-based algorithms to adapt video

bitrates in real-time based on network conditions. However, in environments where network conditions are highly variable, these methods often underperform, resulting in less than optimal user experiences [35, 36].

RL has emerged as a promising technique to address the limitations of heuristic-based approaches. Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of RL algorithms to optimize bitrate adaptation strategies dynamically. For instance, it was proposed a Q-learning-based approach for ABR streaming that outperformed traditional methods in various network scenarios [37]. Similarly, Pensieve was introduced [38], an RL-based system that utilizes neural networks to select bitrates, achieving significant improvements in video QoE compared to conventional algorithms.

PPO algorithm [39], has gained attention for its efficiency and stability in training complex models. It was demonstrated that PPO strikes a better balance between exploration and exploitation in comparison to other RL algorithms [40]. The use of PPO in video bitrate adaptation has shown promising results in simulated environments, providing substantial improvements in QoE metrics [41–44].

Not only that, but this algorithm performs better than other state-of-the-art algorithms [45]. A proposed concept was to examine fluctuations in algorithm performance, as they often exhibit erratic behavior [46].

In parallel, other techniques are explored. Imitation learning has proven to be a valuable approach for RL in scenarios where leveraging expert knowledge accelerates training and improves performance. Techniques such as Comyco [47] and BC-PPO ABR [48] highlight the integration of imitation learning with ABR algorithms for video streaming. Comyco and BC-PPO ABR leverage imitation learning to enhance adaptive bitrate (ABR) decisions, with Comyco achieving superior QoE through lifelong learning and BC-PPO ABR combining behavior cloning and PPO for rapid convergence in dynamic networks.

Self-play RL introduces the ability for agents to train through competition or collaboration, leading to robust and adaptive strategies. Approaches such as Zwei [49], which refines strategies by optimizing win rates in self-play scenarios and CAST [50], that leverages parallel computing to deliver superior QoE in intricate video scenes. Enhanced self-play strategies, including asymmetric self-play, further address challenges in multi-agent environments, ensuring scalability and adaptability in cloud-based systems [51].

Meta-learning, or “learning to learn”, offers a mechanism for RL models to rapidly adapt to heterogeneous conditions with minimal retraining, gaining general knowledge [52]. Several frameworks are proposed, to transferable policies that perform the training in a few trials [53], prioritizing multipath scheduling incorporating both online and offline stages [54,55]

In addition to RL-based methods, NDT environments have been increasingly utilized to replicate real-world network conditions for training and testing video streaming algorithms [14]. These environments provide a controlled setting that mimics network disturbances and performance [56,57], allowing for realistic evaluation of adaptive streaming solutions without impacting actual network performance [58].

Previous studies, such as [59,60], have proposed and demonstrated the effectiveness of using DTs to improve various aspects of network management, including orchestration, performance optimization, and cybersecurity. In recent years, DTs have been studied as a promising alternative for training AI algorithms. In [61], their effectiveness was tested by simulating anomalies in a 5G network, which were then used as input for AI-based cybersecurity tools.

Recent advancements have explored the synergy between NDTs and RL algorithms, leveraging NDTs as virtualized environments for training RL models under various network conditions, such as resource management in vehicular edge computing [62,63], federated learning in mobile networks [64], and computation offloading in IoT systems [65]. NDTs have been instrumental in refining adaptive bitrate (ABR) algorithms by facilitating dynamic reward models that

Fig. 1. Network Digital Twin architecture.

are more closely aligned with user preferences [20] and facilitating large-scale optimization of network coverage using multi-agent RL approaches [66], or even supporting a resource management framework to allow more users under similar congestion performance [67].

3. Methodology

In this section, we detail the architectural components of our proposed system, including the interaction between the physical network and its Digital Twin. We further describe the PPO agent's state space, the formulation of our perceptual-based reward function, and the synchronization mechanism that enables robust sim-to-real policy deployment.

3.1. System architecture

Training is conducted within a NDT, deploying a representation of a network environment as illustrated in Fig. 1. The NDT serves as a controlled yet realistic testing ground. This approach allows an emulation of the network dynamics, including the generation of bandwidth consumption by other users and services, while ensuring that the actual network remains unaffected during the experimental phase. This is important, as the system can experiment with various network conditions and user behaviors, ensuring that the model learns optimal strategies under a variety of scenarios.

Training carried out considered individual delivery for a single user, extracting all metadata involved in a transmission. Based on that, we created a NDT, with most of the components replicated, which consists of the following elements:

- Video source. The origin of the video content that needs to be processed and transmitted. Provides video data to the backend, specifically, to the virtual Compression Engine (vCE) for processing.
- Backend. The server-side system responsible for processing and optimizing the video stream.
 - vCE. Encodes the video content, adapting it for transmission based on the actions of the optimizer.
 - Adaptive Quality Manager (AQM). Optimizer that manages the quality of the video stream dynamically, making adjustments in real-time to ensure optimal streaming quality. Receives feedback from the vCE and Network Performance Probe (NPP) directly via REST API, and consumes data from Video Quality Probe (VQP) using the storage bus.
- Client. The client-side system that receives and processes the video stream for playback and evaluation.

- VQP. Monitors the quality of the video being received and provides feedback on metrics such as blockiness (a measure of tiling patterns caused by heavy compression or low bitrate) and block loss (a count of macroblocks lost or corrupted during transmission). It measures on real-time, and send measurements to storage bus.
- NPP. Monitors the performance of the network, such as throughput, latency, and packet loss. This component is triggered by the AQM to process new measurements. It directs the output to the AQM via a REST API.

- Storage bus. A central repository or communication channel used for storing and transmitting data between components. It is based on an Apache Kafka cluster.
- NDT Manager. The NDT Manager is responsible for managing the synchronization and communication between the virtualized NDT and the physical real network. It operates as a supervisory layer, ensuring that the actions taken in the NDT are based on accurate, real-time data from the physical network, and vice versa. It integrates a feedback loop where it ensures that any adjustments or actions performed in the physical network are reflected back into the NDT.

It is important to note that not all components are replicated symmetrically between the NDT and the real-world architecture. For instance, the AQM is responsible for training and applying intelligence solely within the NDT environment. In the physical network, the actions determined by the AQM in the digital space are applied directly, without additional processing or decision-making. Similarly, the NPP, which serves as an invasive method of monitoring network performance by injecting network packets, only exists within the NDT. In the physical world, this role is changed for end-users to consume the content. Other components, such as the vCE and the VQP are retained in both environments. These elements are essential for sustaining a feedback loop of metadata, enabling the NDT to improve its model and maintain precise control over its physical counterpart.

3.2. Experimental setup

A NDT is an accurate and dynamic digital representation of a telecommunications network, replicating its topology, configuration, behavior and operational state in real or near-real time. This virtual instance is built by integrating analytical models, telemetry data, machine learning algorithms and simulation, enabling emulation, predictive analysis and validation of operational or strategic decisions without directly intervening in the physical network. NDT is used to optimize performance, facilitate automation, reduce diagnostic times, validate control policies and accelerate innovation in complex network environments such as 5G, SDN or NFV.

Fig. 2. Network Digital Twin topology.

In our test environment that will work as NDT we deployed six routers interconnected according to Fig. 2 where we represent a three-hop disaggregation scheme, where the most disaggregated level is the one that connects to the clients and the most central nodes are the ones connected to the content distribution centers (i.e. the source of the video). For the communication between the routers, a BGP/BGP-LS network has been implemented together with OSPF, which allows a hop-by-hop evaluation of the link status. For the end-to-end connectivity, network probes will be used to evaluate metrics such as bandwidth, throughput, packet-loss, latency or jitter through the monitoring of sockets.

The NDT is virtualized in an EVE-NG environment, where both routers and computing devices (servers and clients) are introduced during a configuration phase and the desired values of latency, bandwidth and packet loss per link are defined. EVE-NG was deployed on a virtualized host with an Intel Core i7-12700 CPU and 32 GB of RAM. In order to update the status, the NDT manager reads the status of the links obtained from both BGP-LS and the end-to-end probes (both hosted in the physical network) and triggers a script to update the link capabilities in the virtual environment. This process is performed periodically, based on a configurable refresh interval.

The NDT manages a bandwidth capacity of approximately 35 Mbps per link. This is enough capacity to transmit the prepared video in case that no other services are using the network. A script is developed for the scenario to introduce disturbances, thereby creating varied network conditions. In the high disturbance stage, both high and medium bitrate profiles experience significant disruption, emulating peak usage conditions where multiple services and users compete for bandwidth. The medium disturbance stage restricts this interference to only the highest bitrate profile, mimicking a less congested network scenario. Lastly, the low disturbance stage represents minimal to no interference, offering the model scenarios akin to ideal network conditions.

When the network operator wants to introduce changes in the network, it sends a JSON with the desired changes (both topological or performance changes) to the NDT manager via REST API, with that information and according with the current traffic (or an expected traffic matrix) the NDT can emulate the expected behavior and variation. This capability is automated in the test to make the AI engine the one to define the desired changes and obtain feedback from the results in order to declare a better solution.

The performance values will be also synthesized in Application-Layer Traffic Optimization (ALTO) maps in order to have an exposure

Fig. 3. Physical Twin iterations in yellow and Digital Twin in blue.

technology able to summarize the performance values and return a simplified information document using cost-maps defined in [68]. The ALTO protocol is a standard defined by the IETF that provides topological and network cost information from the service provider's perspective, with the aim of optimizing resource selection by distributed applications. ALTO exposes, through RESTful interfaces, abstractions such as network maps, cost metrics (latency, bandwidth, congestion, etc.) and routing guidelines, allowing external clients to make informed decisions about the optimal placement of servers, traffic routes or access points. This full interaction process is depicted in Fig. 3.

3.3. Multimedia setup

This use case implements a multimedia streaming optimization. Video is stored locally, and delivered on a loop along the whole training. In this case, the video selected is a short film produced by the Blender Foundation called Sintel [69] with some screenshots in Fig. 4. Released in 2010, the film serves as a testament to the capabilities of open-source software, particularly Blender, in creating high-quality animation content.

The content is characterized by a fantasy setting. The film's visual style is characterized by vibrant colors, fantastical landscapes and animated characters. The movie duration is 14 min and 48 s. There are available versions from cinema releases, but there are rendered versions on standard resolutions on wide aspect ratio (21:9), including HD (720p, 1280 × 544 pixels, 6,1 Mbps of bitrate), the analyzed Full HD (FHD) version (1080p, 1920 × 818 pixels, 10,6 Mbps of bitrate), and Ultra HD (UHD) (4K, 4.096 × 1.744 pixels, 40,5 Mbps of bitrate).

For training purposes, we trimmed the credits scenes to focus solely on real scenes, resulting in a final video duration of 12 min and 23 s. In general, the quality of the video between resolutions was almost the same. Metrics were extracted using the personalized VQP, which taking a video as an input, analyzes frame to frame several image features (blockiness, block loss, blur, noise, exposure, contrast, spatial activity and temporal activity).

Fig. 4. Selected screenshots from the video sequence used in the training process.

Fig. 5. Rate Distortion PSNR curves and bitrate across different CRF values.

Video quality metrics are analyzed to feed the RL model, so that it can understand the current situation, not in terms of temporal situation, but in terms of its evaluation and assessment. Originally, this content has an average bitrate of 10.6 Mbps, which increases to 11.2 Mbps when the credits scenes are removed.

However, video content is transcoded using the vCE tool with FFmpeg, an open-source platform for recording, converting, and streaming multimedia. The transcoding process is configured for ultrafast processing and zero latency with a Constant Rate Factor (CRF) of 10, ensuring smooth real-time transmission. After transcoding, the video’s bitrate increases to 39.8 Mbps. In some scenarios, this bitrate is too high for practical transmission. To address this, a range of lower bitrates is considered to assess the content’s quality, considering an upper-limit for highest quality, and the lower one for reduced bitrate.

Fig. 5 illustrates the rate–distortion sweep obtained by encoding the sequence with different CRF values, from 0 (visually lossless) to 51 (maximum compression). Average Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) (blue) and minimum PSNR (green) decline almost linearly with CRF, whereas the corresponding bitrate (orange, right-hand axis) falls much faster from around 90 Mbps at CRF 0 to 1 Mbps beyond CRF 36. We adopted CRF 10 as our reference point because it delivers virtually source-level quality (≈ 52.31 dB average PSNR) while capping the bitrate at 39.8 Mbps, a level still sustainable by the testbed.

In addition to bitrate and PSNR, the same CRF analysis was compared against blockiness and block loss (see Fig. 6), allowing us to relate perceptual quality metrics with a standard signal-based reference. Across the range of CRF values, blockiness varied between approximately 0.5 and 0.94, while block loss spanned from 0 up to 500. Aligning these perceptual measures with PSNR improves the generalization of our analysis, as it situates distortions within a widely recognized quality scale. This joint view shows that while PSNR decreases almost linearly with CRF, perceptual artifacts such as blockiness and block loss evolve non-linearly, highlighting their added value for reward function design and QoE evaluation.

Among all the quality metrics available, four are those that are capable of statically representing the quality of the image. Therefore, these metrics are what we use to evaluate the quality of each video after receiving a significant bitrate reduction. Other features like temporal activity are the same between bitrates, as bitrate compression does not

(a) Blockiness

(b) Block loss

Fig. 6. Comparison of PSNR for different CRF values, together with blockiness and block loss.

affect it. Based on Fig. 7, we reached an understanding to determine the streaming bitrate. In this way, we can establish and decide which are the optimal quality thresholds to decide the future quality profiles of the optimization system.

The highest bitrate considered for initial testing is 30 Mbps, slightly below the original transcoded rate, yet comparably close. In terms of quality, it was almost the same for all the characteristics. There are hardly any notable differences between the first profiles, so the primary challenge is to select the lowest quality profile. That is, a profile that has sufficient quality, resulting in quality losses. In the contrary, we discovered that the 5 Mbps profile is an example where the block loss significantly increases. We need to select those profiles, that in case of no problems in transmission, the quality is adequate.

The profiles need to be distinct enough to cause variations in the quality metric values. Normally, the system should transmit at the maximum bitrate, but if link capacity is insufficient, it must automatically adjust the bitrate to enhance the end user’s QoE. Fig. 8 shows the evolution along the complete sequence of the main image metrics to evaluate quality, but in this case, for the three selected profiles, 25, 15 and 7 Mbps.

Fig. 7. Media summary of key video quality metrics for different bitrate values of the video.

The choice of three distinct bitrate profiles (High, Medium, and Low) in this study is deliberate and supported by previous research [28], which indicates that an excessive number of profiles can obscure the agent’s ability to map network conditions to clear quality representations. Categorizing the action space into three well-defined perceptual tiers, we can ensure that the PPO agent can establish a stable policy baseline. This categorization prevents the overlapping of quality states, allowing the model to focus on the fundamental trade-offs between throughput availability and perceptual artifacts like blockiness.

3.4. Reinforcement learning algorithm design

This case evolves RL optimization strategies by using one of the latest RL algorithms, PPO, and including network aspects that can improve both stability and training times. Therefore, the core of our approach was to train a policy that decides the optimal bitrate for streamed content, adapting to changes in network status.

The proposed PPO algorithm adopts a two-head Actor–Critic architecture: an actor that outputs a Soft-max probability over the available bitrate actions and a critic that returns a single state-value estimate. Both heads receive the same observation vector comprising the current quality level, buffer size, and network telemetry, and each is built from two fully connected layers of 32 units with tanh activations. Parameters are updated with Adam (learning rate of 0.001), using a clip ratio of 0.2 and the usual value of discount factor of 0.99.

Training data was collected from an environment designed to model typical internet video streaming scenarios. This custom-built emulation varied network conditions and client behavior to provide a novel set of states for a RL training. The state space was defined as a vector composed of three groups of features: (i) image quality metrics (Blockiness, Spatial Activity, Block Loss, Blur, Temporal Activity, Noise, Exposure, Contrast); (ii) streaming resources (Current bitrate, Maximum bitrate, Encoding Quality, CPU usage, RAM usage); and (iii) network status (Throughput, Packet loss, Latency). These states were updated every 10–15 s to reflect system dynamics under varying network and client conditions. The action space was discrete, allowing the agent to select among three predefined bitrate profiles: 25 Mbps (action 0), 15 Mbps (action 1), and 7 Mbps (action 2). This explicit definition ensures that the agent observes a comprehensive view of video quality, resource usage, and network performance when making adaptation decisions.

After each action is committed, the algorithm waits for the streaming to stabilize before collecting data. This stabilization period ensures that the impact of the action on the streaming quality can be accurately

assessed. Data is then gathered from various sources through a REST API. The vCE handles the action and provides the streaming resources metrics. Concurrently, all image quality metrics are consumed from a Kafka stream published by the VQP. Finally, the NPP is triggered via a REST API to measure the quality of the network.

The reward function was designed with several key components, each targeting a specific aspect of the streaming experience. These components aimed to ensure that the algorithm’s actions, which involved adjusting the video bitrate, led to an optimal balance between video quality and network performance.

Firstly, the reward function included a component for blockiness, a measure of visual artifacts in the video stream. The goal was to minimize blockiness, thus improving the perceived quality of the video. The reward for blockiness was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Rwd}_{\text{Blockiness}} = \begin{cases} 20 \times B & \text{if } B > 0.8 \\ 10 \times B & \text{if } B > 0.6 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where B denotes for Blockiness metric. Secondly, the reward function accounted for block loss, which represents the loss of video frames and significantly impacts the viewing experience. The reward for block loss was designed to penalize high block loss values:

$$\text{Rwd}_{\text{BlockLoss}} = \max(2 \times (5 - \text{BL}), -50). \quad (2)$$

and BL stands for Block Loss. An additional component of the reward function was the profile reward, which incentivized the selection of appropriate bitrate profiles based on current network conditions. This was especially important to prevent the algorithm from adopting overly conservative bitrate strategies that might degrade the user experience:

$$\text{Rwd}_{\text{Profile}} = \begin{cases} 10 & \text{if } B > 0.7 \text{ and} \\ & \text{BL} < 5.0 \text{ and} \\ & \text{Action} = 0 \\ 5 & \text{if } B > 0.7 \text{ and} \\ & \text{BL} < 5.0 \text{ and} \\ & \text{Action} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The total reward was the sum of these individual rewards, reflecting a comprehensive assessment of the streaming quality. The reward functions emphasized video quality, with Eq. (1) addressing blockiness [70] and Eq. (2) targeting block loss [71]. These metrics quantify image fidelity by penalizing visual artifacts and frame loss, and their thresholds were set in accordance with the guidelines of the quality assessment tool employed for video evaluation. The penalty for block loss was set high to strongly discourage actions that severely degrade QoE, while blockiness values were weighted to distinguish between good quality ($B > 0.6$) and excellent quality ($B > 0.8$), assigning zero reward below 0.6 to reflect unacceptable visual quality.

The reward function is bounded between a maximum of 40 (perfect delivery) and a minimum of -50 (severe quality degradation). These bounds were selected to provide a dense reward signal that prevents the convergence issues often associated with sparse rewards in RL, while remaining strictly tied to the perceptual thresholds established by the VQP.

For training purposes, the video was stored locally and streamed. Each training episode comprised a set of 20 steps. If the video concluded before reaching 20 steps, the environment signaled that the episode was done, triggering an update to the records. This approach ensured that the PPO algorithm received frequent updates, allowing it to learn and adapt efficiently to the streaming environment.

Each episode concluded either after 20 steps or once the video ended, whichever occurred first. This structured method of training allowed the algorithm to balance the length of episodes, ensuring that learning was consistent and that the policy updates reflected a diverse set of video playback scenarios.

Fig. 8. Multimedia features comparison across selected bitrate profiles.

4. Results

The following section presents a quantitative evaluation of the NDT-PPO agent’s performance. We provide a detailed analysis of its behavior under various network congestion patterns.

The initial plot for the results is presented in Fig. 9. It shows the reward progression over 150 episodes in the training phase of the algorithm. The *x*-axis represents the episodes or iterations during the training process, while the *y*-axis denotes the reward values. As the reward function is tailored to reflect the QoE, a higher reward indicates better user experience in terms of video streaming quality, and other states considered in the design of the reward functions.

As the training progresses, the reward exhibits some fluctuations, which is typical in RL training due to the exploration-exploitation trade-off. However, the general trend shows an upward trajectory, indicating that the algorithm becomes more proficient at selecting actions that enhance the QoE. The final part of the plot shows the reward stabilizing with minor fluctuations around a higher value, which suggests that the RL algorithm has effectively learned to make decisions that optimize the QoE for the video streaming application. This behavior signifies a successful training phase, preparing the algorithm for deployment in real-world scenarios.

Along the whole training, it is useful to evaluate the evolution of the actions taken. In Fig. 10, the histogram depicts the count of each profile action (0, 1, and 2) taken by the RL algorithm during the training period, which took around 600 min for completion of 150 steps. However, once trained, the inference time is negligible, making it suitable for real-time edge deployment. Initially, there was a higher frequency of profile action 2, indicating a preference for

Fig. 9. Reward values over training.

lower bitrates, possibly due to the algorithm’s exploratory phase. As time progresses, the counts of actions 0 and 1 increase, suggesting the algorithm’s transition towards exploiting better-performing actions. This coincides with the decay of policy entropy, that after several steps, the exploration wanes. A balanced selection in general across profiles indicates that the algorithm adapts to varying network conditions and user demands. But also is exposed a slight skewed selection of profile 0 in latest steps, suggesting a preference for this particular profile, which is motivated by the algorithm’s learned behavior.

Following the analysis of the action selection and the reward learning process, we now turn to evaluate the performance metrics captured during the training. Fig. 11 presents scatter plots that highlight

Fig. 10. Histogram of actions over training.

the relationships between multimedia metrics such as block loss and blockiness, as well as their correlation with network conditions like throughput, packet loss, and latency. Also are considered the different actions taken by the RL algorithm. In the upper-left subplot, block loss is plotted against blockiness. At least in terms of actions, there is not direct relationship between these two metrics.

The upper right subplot illustrates block loss in relation to throughput. Lower throughput values tend to correspond with higher block loss, particularly when throughput drops below 10 Mbps. Actions 1 and 2 show more dispersion in block loss, allowing the network probe to measure higher bitrates. By contrast, action 0 maintains, generally, block loss values lower than 20, but, as expected, comprises the network in throughput values lower than 10.

In the bottom left part of the figure, block loss is exposed with packet loss. There is a direct connection with these metrics, and higher packet loss percentages are strongly correlated with increased block loss. There are some appearances for action 2 when packet loss are less than 20%, but most of the block losses in the image are present when the measured packet loss in 100%. This is the case of actions 0 and 1 specially, as they tend to fill the available bandwidth on the network.

Finally, the bottom right shows block loss with the last network metric, latency. Actions are dispersed along the axis, where most of the action 0 values are present in very high values of latency, with some of them presenting block loss in the image. Actions 1 and 2 primarily occur at lower latency ranges, whereas action 0 typically results in a latency of 1000 ms. One big remark, is that when the latencies are 0, there are too much block losses. This can be likely caused by execution of the network probe.

One of the critical aspects to analyze in an RL algorithm is whether it has become overly conservative or has learned to properly distribute actions based on the states of the environment. In this study, the training phase refers to the process of training the model and obtaining the reward function, while the production phase involves applying the trained model to a real-world environment to evaluate its performance and ensure it has been trained effectively.

In Fig. 12, the distribution of actions is compared between these two phases. During the training phase, the algorithm primarily favors actions 0 and 2, with frequencies around 40% and 35%, respectively, while action 1 is less frequent at approximately 25%. This distribution indicates that the algorithm explores both higher and lower bitrates extensively, with a moderate selection of the medium bitrate.

In the production phase, action 0 maintains a high frequency of around 40%, indicating a consistent preference for the highest bitrate, similar to the training phase. However, the frequency of action 2 decreases to about 20%, while the frequency of action 1 increases to approximately 40%. This indicates the algorithm adapts its strategy in real-world conditions by balancing high and medium bitrates more effectively.

One of the objectives of applying RL techniques, was to improve the QoE of the streaming, with specially focus on blockiness and block loss. A reduction, or values close to 0 on block loss means that the algorithm effectively minimizes visual artifacts and frame losses, whereas blockiness values close to 1.0, derive in good image quality. These two metrics are measured in Fig. 13, comparing the data obtained during training phase, and checking the improvements obtained when the model was trained and employed on production.

For the blockiness metric, both phases exhibit similar values, with blockiness around 0.9. This high value indicates good image quality in both phases, suggesting that the RL algorithm consistently maintains a high level of video quality. For the block loss metric, there is a noticeable improvement from training to production. The average block loss decreases from approximately 7.0 during training to around 2.5 in the production phase. This significant reduction in block loss indicates fewer losses in content under real-world conditions, having learned to improve the content delivery.

Finally, in order to complete the efficiency and performance of the algorithm, we evaluate the percentage of actions taken under different background bitrate conditions. First, the training phase is presented in Fig. 14(a). Under a background bitrate of 1000, action 2 is preferred around 50%, with action 0 very close, with percentage values of 40%. There are not many differences when the bitrate background increases to 5.000, but the more noticeable change is in 15,000 value of background bitrate, where action 2 becomes the most dominant at around 70%.

On the production step, and depicted in Fig. 14(b) under a background bitrate of 1000, the actions are relatively evenly distributed, with action 0 at around 40%, action 1 at about 35%, and action 2 at roughly 25%. As the background bitrate increases to 5000, the algorithm predominantly favors action 0 (about 70%), with actions 1 and 2 significantly less frequent. At the highest background bitrate of 15,000, action 1 becomes dominant at around 70%, with actions 0 and 2 much less frequent. This change suggests the algorithm's adaptation to optimize QoE, as high background traffic causes a degradation on the image quality, and optimizer reduces adequately the bitrate of the main streaming. This is a notable shift from the training phase where action 2 was more frequent, motivated by the exploration nature of RL algorithms.

Finally, all the results are summarized in Table 1. We report the results comparing both the training and production stages relative to the total values, and also including the percentage enhancement between training and production in the final column. The metrics evaluated include blockiness, block loss, bitrate, and reward. Blockiness values are slightly increased for a 6.40%, but they represent the lowest improvement in comparison with the rest of the metrics.

Block loss, a critical indicator of content loss, significantly decreased from 7.72% during training to 2.55% in production, yielding an impressive improvement of 66.87%. This substantial reduction in block loss underscores the RL algorithm's optimization. The bitrate metric also improved, rising from 15.24 Mbps during training to 18.41 Mbps in production, an increase of 17.18%, motivated mainly by the frequency of actions for highest profile in the deployment.

Finally, the reward metric, which encapsulates the overall performance and QoE optimization, shows the most substantial improvement, increasing from 16.60 in training to 28.74 mean reward value in production, resulting in a 73.02% improvement. This significant boost in reward highlights the algorithm's effectiveness.

To provide statistical validation for our performance claims, we performed a two-sample t-test to compare the means of the training and production data for each metric. The results confirm that the substantial reduction in block loss ($p = 0.004$) is statistically significant, validating our primary objective to minimize content loss. Additionally, the overall system performance, encapsulated by the reward metric ($p = 0.007$), also showed a statistically significant improvement. Conversely, the p-values for blockiness ($p = 0.107$) and bitrate ($p = 0.370$) were greater

Fig. 11. Scatter plots illustrating the relationships between block loss, blockiness, and key network metrics along with the actions taken.

Fig. 12. Actions frequency distribution comparison between training and production.

Fig. 13. QoE evaluation and comparison between training and production.

than 0.05, indicating that the observed differences in these metrics are not statistically significant. The blockiness metric was already within acceptable thresholds during the training phase, making further significant improvements less critical. For bitrate, the high standard deviation and lack of statistical significance are attributed to the nature of the FFmpeg encoder, where the chosen action represents an objective bitrate, but the video's actual bitrate can fluctuate depending on the complexity of the scene, leading to natural variability that the model is designed to handle.

Fig. 14. Histogram of next actions taken based on network background conditions. (a) Training. (b) Production.

Table 1 Comparison of algorithm results.

KPI	Train.	Prod.	Δ (%)	p -value
Blockiness (%)	87.5 \pm 10.1	93.0 \pm 7.0	6.4	0.107
Block loss (%)	7.7 \pm 11.2	2.5 \pm 4.8	-66.8	0.004
Bitrate (Mbps)	15.2 \pm 8.4	18.4 \pm 8.1	17.1	0.370
Reward (Mean)	16.6 \pm 24.4	28.7 \pm 14.6	73.0	0.007

5. Discussion

While previous section focused on the technical execution of the tests, this section interprets the performance gains, analyzes the agent's adaptability to non-stationarity, and compares the results against representative RL-based ABR models.

The experimental evidence shows that the joint PPO and NDT workflow delivers a 73% rise in the composite reward and cuts block-loss by roughly two-thirds. This gain stems from four mutually reinforcing design choices. First, the on-policy nature of PPO with clipped updates and entropy regularization, keeps the actor-critic stable, so reward

Table 2
Comparison of NDT-PPO against SOTA ABR Algorithms.

Approach	Algorithm	Limitation Addressed	Gain
Q-Learning [37]	Q-Learning	Unstable policy updates	Low stability
Pensieve [38]	A3C	Fixed trace dependency	Sim-to-real gap
Twin-RL [20]	RL + Twin	Purely theoretical/simulated	No live validation
Meta-RL [41]	Meta-RL	High architectural overhead	Topology-specific
Proposed	PPO + NDT	N/A (Integrated Workflow)	+6.4 (Blockiness), -66.8 Block loss

climbs smoothly instead of oscillating as it does for earlier Q-learning or vanilla A3C agents [37,40]. Second, pre-training inside a high-fidelity NDT eliminates the customary cold-start window [22]: the policy arrives in production already able to select the highest 25 Mbps profile in 40% of decisions, yet still downgrades decisively when congestion appears. Third, the reward mixes perceptual terms (blockiness and block-loss) with a bitrate bonus, so the agent learns to raise quality and suppress artifacts simultaneously.

A closer look at the logged telemetry confirms that the policy adapts meaningfully to network stress. Scatter plots reveal that block-loss spikes only when throughput drops below 10 Mbps or packet-loss exceeds 20%; in those stages the agent almost always chooses the conservative 7 Mbps profile, containing visual damage to $\leq 20\%$ even at 100 ms latency. During live operation the action histogram shifts from an exploration-heavy preference for the lowest profile to a balanced 40%/40% split between the two higher profiles, indicating that the model exploited favorable links while still preserving a safety margin under load.

When compared against five representative approaches, the contribution of this work becomes clearer. Table 2 summarizes the key distinctions and performance gains. Compared with Q-learning ABR [37] the clipped surrogate in PPO prevents destructive policy updates; against Pensieve's trace-trained A3C [38] the NDT supplies real-time topology feedback, shrinking the sim-to-real gap; in a twin-assisted RL [20] remains confined to simulation, whereas our policy is shown to cut live block-loss by 66%; meta-RL schemes [41] introduce extra complexity to generalize across topologies, while our twin encapsulates that diversity implicitly; and behavior-cloned PPO [48] converges faster but plateaus at a lower QoE (2.8–3.7 versus 6.4 in blockiness).

6. Conclusion

In this study, we explored the application of PPO, a RL algorithm, to optimize QoE in video streaming scenarios. Video bitrate was adjusted dynamically in response to fluctuating network conditions. After carrying out a training, the results demonstrated significant improvements in key video quality metrics. Specifically, the algorithm achieved a 66.87% reduction in block loss from training to production, and a 6.40% improvement in blockiness, ensuring a higher overall video quality for end users.

Integrating a NDT environment for training was important, as it simulated real-world disruptions without impacting actual network performance. This provided a testing space for the RL model to learn optimal strategies under different network conditions. As a result, the algorithm was able to balance the trade-offs between video quality and network performance, achieving a 73.02% increase in the reward metric, which encapsulates the overall QoE improvement.

Despite these advancements, there are opportunities for further optimization. While the PPO algorithm effectively adapts to network variations, future work could explore more advanced state representations or alternative RL algorithms (Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C); Soft

Actor-Critic (SAC)) to further enhance the performance. Additionally, incorporating more complex network metrics, such as real-time congestion patterns and more granular user feedback, could provide a deeper understanding of QoE dynamics in larger-scale deployments.

While the current implementation utilizes a set of three profile bitrate selection, the architecture is inherently scalable to more complex, multi-level ABR scenarios. Our framework can be viewed as a Level 1 controller that establishes the broad quality category. In a production-grade multi-level deployment, each primary tier could act as a parent class, where a secondary sub-selection process, based on fine-grained parameters such as frame rate or specific content complexity, further refines the delivery. This hierarchical approach would allow for even more granular QoE optimization without sacrificing the training stability demonstrated in this work.

The success of the NDT environment also opens up avenues for investigating its use in more complex streaming architectures, particularly with the growing demands of 5G and beyond. Future research could focus on applying these methods to multi-Content Delivery Network (CDN) environments, where content delivery paths can dynamically change, or to real-time applications such as live streaming, where latency and stability are even more critical.

Two practical upgrades will align the solution with AI-for-6G ambitions. First, extend the twin with real-time RAN telemetry and deploy the model on GPU-enabled edge nodes; this would exploit URLLC slices to keep inference and reaction below 5 ms, crucial for XR and interactive live events. Second, turn the single-site twin into a federated, multi-CDN fabric where edge clusters share gradients but keep user data local. That architecture would let the agent weigh bitrate and path-selection actions jointly, optimize latency and energy-cost trade-offs on the fly, and continue learning online as networks, codecs and carbon targets evolve.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alberto del Rio: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Alejandro Muñiz:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Javier Serrano:** Validation, Conceptualization. **David Jimenez:** Validation. **Luis Miguel Contreras:** Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Alberto del Rio reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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